

THEORY OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN IT.

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Abstract: This article discusses the credit-module system, which is considered a new system in the higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan today, and the history of its origin. It is said that the main purpose of its application is to ensure transparency and openness in higher education..

Key words: credit module, mobility, transparency, ECTS, Bologna Declaration, Charles Elliot

It is known that in our country, special attention is being paid to the field of education, including the dedication of higher education, its transparency, and improvement of the system related to the organization of the educational process. The State President of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev approved the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 and the Action Strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 "Science, Enlightenment and development of the digital economy" on March 2, 2020, was set to set a number of tasks in the Decree No. PF 5953. One of the priority and most important tasks was to gradually transfer the educational process to the credit module system in higher education institutions.

The credit module system was considered a novelty for higher education, a new stage of education. The reason is that higher education is surrounded by red tape left over from the Soviet era and some subjects that have lost their relevance today and are not accepted by today's marketing. The credit system in higher education is aimed at making the quality of education, studies and courses more open and transparent. Another aspect of the system is that it is student-oriented education, that is, it perfects the student's mobility. In addition, the credit module system combines several types of educational opportunities and provides students with the prospect of continuous education..

It's no secret that everything has a history of its creation, and the credit module system is no exception. Its first roots go back to the USA. The credit-module system created in it is considered one of the first to be introduced, and it contributed to the formation of the credit-module system in higher education institutions of the world countries, including European countries. So what was the reason for the establishment of the credit-module system in America? Of

course, in the universities of that time, subjects that had lost their importance in practice, including Latin, which had already become a dead language by that time, were taught as a separate language. And as a result, universities have turned into a place where representatives of the upper class study for authority, rather than a training center that benefits the state. This changed in 1869, when Charles Elliott, a progressive thinker of the time, was elected president of Harvard University. He canceled the strictly defined educational programs at the university and gave students the opportunity to choose and learn the subjects they want and are interested in from among the subjects offered in the curriculum. This is how Harvard University came to life. The reason is that students are satisfied with the fact that they are learning the subjects they want and are important in the market economy, and at the same time, the teachers had to make unusual and effective transitions in their subjects and research on them in order to interest the students. In this way, the subjects with a low level of importance for that period were removed from the curriculum. However, the university has given up strict educational programs, and questions about the order of the student's transition from course to course and graduation criteria, and how much knowledge a student should acquire in order to become a specialist. At that time, Harvard University came up with the following solution to this question: i.e., symbolic measurement units (credits) were distributed to each subject based on its academic load. And it is determined that the student must accumulate a certain number of credits. And this begins to determine the development of educational programs of students, their suitability for a certain level of education, depending on the number of credits they have accumulated.

European countries also developed a new ECTS (European Credit Transfer System) in 1989, based on the American credit system and the Dutch higher education system. As a result of the introduction of the rules of this credit-module system, the exchange of students between the universities of the European Union countries began to develop.

By 1999, an international forum for developing mutual cooperation between the ministries of higher education of European countries, called the Bologna Process, will begin work. According to it, in order to improve and improve the quality of education, to ensure transparency, the three-level "bachelor-master-doctor" structure of training of specialists is implemented in two stages according to the single credit education system: higher education (bachelor's-master's degree) and post-secondary education (doctor).

Organization of student-oriented education, achieving transparency in education, increasing flexibility in education and increasing student mobility are the principles of the credit-module system. In conclusion, maintaining the credit module system in higher education is a beneficial way for both the teacher and the university.

References:

1. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2020). Technologies of developing the ecological culture of students in the process of learning a foreign languages in higher educational institutions. *Solid State Technology*, 63(1s), 1816-1825.
2. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2021). Analysis of Effective Ways to Develop Students' Environmental Culture in Foreign Language Teaching. *Central asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture*, 2(12), 37-43.
3. Обидова, Г. (2021). Развитие экологической культуры в образовательных моделях развитых стран мира. *Общество и инновации*, 2(10/S), 251-256.
4. Tadjibaeva, A., & Tashlanova, N. (2020). The collaborative approach in content and language learning. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (6 (60)), 31-34.
5. Mamatovich, Z. R., & Ergashevna, T. A. (2019). Blended learning in higher education using LMS Moodle. *Образовательный процесс*, (5 (16)), 5-9.
6. Ergashevna, T. A. (2020). Specific features of the language in the development of culture. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (3 (148)), 82-84.
7. Mukhammad, K. K., & ogli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022, December). THE ESSENCE OF NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES (Vol. 1, No. 19, pp. 91-93)*.
8. ogli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). HISTORICAL AND MODERN CLASSIFICATION OF PARALINGUISTICS. *Academia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3 (10), 126-128.
9. Sarvinoz, T., & Shodiya, I. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA KOGNITIV LINGVISTIKA SHAKLLANISH TARIXIGA DOIR. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(13), 51-54.
10. Ibragimjonovna, A. M. (2023). The Issues Related to Studying of Language and thought in Cognitive Linguistics. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 31, 271-273.
11. Toshpulatova, M., & Ilhomjonova, R. (2023). TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY. *Engineering problems and innovations*.
12. Toshpulatova, M. I. (2022). The main features in teaching English for specific purposes. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(5), 207-214.
13. Ikromovna, T. M. (2022). USE OF FOLKTALES IN ENGLISH LESSONS. *POLISH SCIENCE JOURNAL*, 88.

14. Parpiyeva, M., & Jurayeva, M. (2023). Problems of linguoculturological and neurolinguistic study of phonetic means. *American Journal Of Philological Sciences*, 3(02), 49-59.
15. Abdug'ofur qizi Jurayeva, M., & SultanovnaUsmanova, S. (2023). Neyrolingvistika sohasini organish tendensiyalari. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 2(1), 53-59.
16. Abdug'ofur qizi Jurayeva, M., & Alisher o'g'li, M. M. (2023). Morphology and syntax and crosslinguistic findings in neurolinguistics. *Образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире*, 18(8), 156-159.
17. Dilshoda, R. (2022). THE STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF COMPUTER TERMS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 20(2), 36-40.
18. Raximjonova, D. (2022). INGLIZ VA O 'ZBEK TILLARIDA KOMPOZITSIYA USULIDA SO 'Z YASALISHI HODISASINING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(4), 710-713.
19. Raximjonova, D. (2023). STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF COMPUTER SOFTWARE TERMS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. *Farg 'ona davlat universiteti ilmiy jurnali*, (1), 448-452.
20. Djuraevna, T. N. (2023). The Cognitive Aspect of the Purpose of Teaching Foreign Languages. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 16, 88-94.
21. Djuraevna, T. N. (2023). Language Education as A System: Structure, Functions and Main Components. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 14, 141-146.
22. Djurayevna, T. N. (2022). Semantic and structural features of the vocabulary of color designation in english, uzbek and russian languages. *Global Book Publishing Services*, 01-123.
23. Juraeva, Z. Q. (2017). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF LANGUAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURE. *Форум молодых ученых*, (5 (9)), 5-9.